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INCREASING THE QUALITY OF SERVICE IN RURAL AREAS - AS AN ECONOMIC FACTOR

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Abstract. The article describes the theoretical and practical aspects of improving the quality of service in rural areas. The data are compiled based on the author's observations and analysis of foreign literature. The methodological basis of the research was formed as a result of the study of theoretical and practical information, legislation and other legal documents, literary sources and publications. The research is based on the connections between theory and practice and made extensive use of analysis, comparison, and synthesis methods.

Keywords. Rural Area, Service, Service, Provision Of Services, Factor, Quality, Competition, Trade, Network, Development, Employment, Infrastructure.

I. INTRODUCTION

Along with the increase in population and the quality of living conditions in our country, the demand for quality services is also growing. It is especially important to improve the quality of existing services in rural areas and establish new service enterprises.

The level of development of services reflects the socio-economic situation in the country.

Today, along with population growth, the demand for services is also growing. At the same time, we can see an increase in the quality of services provided to the population with the development of digital technologies. Nevertheless, we can observe some services' poor quality or non-availability in our country.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The following scholars have considered increasing the quality of service in rural areas in their research: Makhmudov L.U., Rakhimov Z.K. [3].

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodological basis of the research was formed as a result of the study of theoretical and practical information, legislation and other legal documents, literary sources and publications. The research is based on the connections between theory and practice and made extensive use of analysis, comparison, and synthesis methods.

IV. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

From 2016-to 2020, it is planned to increase the gross domestic product of the Republic of Uzbekistan through the development of the service sector, increase its share in the economy to 48.7% and increase the service sector in rural areas 1.8 times by 2020.

It is known that at present the services are mainly developed in cities. For this reason, the program attaches great importance to the full development of the service

sector in rural areas. After all, the rural population's living standards and quality of life cannot be realized without developing the service sector¹.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 No PF-4947 "On the Action Strategy for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan"² Over the years, great attention has been paid to the development of services based on socio-economic development programs in the regions of the country, the creation of new jobs in this area.

At present, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 of January 28, 2022, "On the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026,"³ "... Strengthening social protection and reducing poverty has been identified as a priority of public policy, providing the population with new jobs and a guaranteed source of income, qualified medical and educational services, decent living conditions to a qualitatively new level."⁴ Therefore, special attention is paid to the socio-economic development of the population by improving citizens' quality of life, providing them with jobs, and providing qualified personnel for the service sector.

Today, 65-75 percent of human consumer goods are various services. The development of digital technologies also contributes to the sharp increase in demand for services. Examples of such technologies are communication and information services.

It is known that service providers, unlike other material producers, do not spend a lot of money on the organization of their activities. Therefore, it is possible to organize service entities in rural areas based on the population's capabilities, taking into account their resources and conditions. This can be achieved by conducting short-term outreach to the rural population to engage in service entrepreneurship, organizing training courses with the involvement of relevant specialists from universities, and ensuring cooperation with enterprises that have been working effectively in this field for years.

The organization of digital services in rural areas will save some costs for newly established businesses. This will help reduce the cost of services provided to people living in rural areas.

Strict quarantine measures were introduced in our country in 2020-2021 due to the spread of coronavirus infection (COVID-19). Therefore, the entrepreneurs of our country have managed to reduce costs for placing and receiving orders from traditional trade through digital technologies and the storage of goods. In these years, the share of "Elnur", which provides some trade and services in rural areas, is 20.8-22.1%⁵,

¹Information of Annexes 1-2 to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 26, 2016 No. 55 "On the program of development of the service sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2016-2020".

² <https://lex.uz/docs/3107036>

³ <https://lex.uz/docs/5841063>

⁴There

⁵Data of "Elnur" OK for 2020-2021.

“Mohigul-Parfum” OK 11.3-15.6 percent⁶, Prestige LLC 13.4-15.6 percent⁷ subjects have managed to reduce the cost of storing goods.

Today, we can see that the infrastructure in rural areas is not developed enough to provide services. For example, in the cultivation of agricultural products, the severity of the requirements for maintenance, financing, insurance of agricultural products, and the lack of quality Internet services are examples.

Improving the living standards and quality of life in rural areas in our country depends on the activities of production, services, and infrastructure. For this reason, the study of consumer needs of the rural population and their fuller satisfaction is one of the important issues.

In developed economies, special government programs are adopted to provide services to the rural population and improve the living standards of the rural population. For example, the United States pays special attention to constructing service facilities in rural areas, where infrastructure facilities are created to create a new business environment. European countries focus on developing agro-tourism during the cultivation of agricultural products on farms and peasant farms in rural areas. In other words, foreign tourists interested in growing agricultural products have the opportunity to participate in the process of growing agricultural products directly. This,

In 2018, U.S. President Trump set himself the goal of further improving U.S. infrastructure. Trump has proposed allocating 25 percent of the new money in the U.S., or \$ 50 billion, to interest-free rural infrastructure development. This is an unprecedented offer. His proposal encourages spending at least \$ 1.5 trillion over the next 10 years to develop infrastructure in rural areas.

The U.S. Congress accepted President Trump’s proposal. The proposal, passed by Congress, was approved by Trump in March 2018 and included in the 2018 budget plan, and it is a broad-based, robust \$ 600 million investment. These funds will serve as the initial investment in the proposal made by the President to improve it in the coming months⁸ and will be considered again.

It is known that, unlike other countries, our country has a unique approach to the development of infrastructure services. At present, special attention is paid to the development of this sector in our country. In particular, it is planned to improve the living standards of the population, improve the service of manufacturing and non-manufacturing enterprises, as well the quality of their activities in all regions of the country.

Today, infrastructure facilities are also important for the employment of the population in rural areas and the establishment of new products and service enterprises in those areas. However, it was found that a favorable production and service (infrastructure) environment has not been created for entrepreneurs engaged in entrepreneurial activities to organize quality service in rural areas.

⁶Data of Mohigul-Parfum OK for 2020-2021.

⁷Data of Prestige LLC for 2020-2021.

⁸ <https://www.usda.gov/media/press-releases/2018/03/23/secretary-perdue-applauds-broadband-investment-included-omnibus>

It is known that the provision of services through digital technologies reduces the costs of businesses and leads to lower prices for goods and services offered to consumers. At the same time, convenience will be created for the consumer to use various services. Such technologies make it easier for new entrepreneurs to enter the market and attract customers in a highly competitive environment at a lower cost in setting up new businesses.

Through digital technologies, the entrepreneur will be able to use the feedback method and get direct feedback from consumers about their products and services quickly.

In short, to organize service in rural areas, it is necessary to use digital technologies in the country, study in depth and introduce quality services in developed countries, and use the feedback method to constantly and quickly study the views of entrepreneurs and consumers.

V. CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

To improve the quality of service in rural areas, we can offer the following:

- introduction of digital technologies in rural areas;
- organization of quality Internet services for businesses in rural areas to operate through digital technologies;
- to create national online platforms and programs for doing business;
- organization of feedback in rural areas.

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